

FLUCTUATING HEAT FLUX MEASUREMENTS IN AN INCIDENT SHOCK/BOUNDARY-LAYER INTERACTION

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ABSTRACT

We present measurements of fluctuating heat flux in a turbulent, incident shock/boundary-layer interaction (SBLI) at $Ma = 2.0$ using fast-response ALTP (Atomic Layer Thermo Pile) sensors. The unsteadiness over a broad range of frequencies is captured and compared against state of the art fluctuating pressure measurements. While low-frequency unsteadiness at $St_{L_{int}} \approx 0.05$ is visible near the separation shock foot, the maximum amplitude is observed in the reattachment zone at medium frequencies ($St_{L_{int}} \approx 1$). This is a key difference between the heat flux and pressure signatures which points toward different mechanisms responsible for local unsteadiness.

1. INTRODUCTION

Modern supersonic and hypersonic vehicles encounter shock/boundary layer interactions (SBLI) in a variety of configurations. Such complex flows are typically characterized by unsteadiness in a broad range of frequencies. Perhaps one of the most intriguing aspects of SBLIs is the presence of pressure fluctuations at frequencies about two decades lower than the upstream boundary-layer fluctuations when the flow is separated [1, 2]. This phenomenon has been linked to detrimental effects like fatigue loading or panel flutter (e.g. [3]) and has major implications in the design process of high-speed vehicles.

While it is commonly assumed that pressure fluctuations occurring in separated SBLIs are linked to temperature or heat flux variations at the vehicle surface, unsteadiness in thermal variables has not been thoroughly investigated so far. Part of the reason is probably the difficulty of measuring temperature or heat flux with a bandwidth sufficient to capture the fluctuations occurring in supersonic flows

that can be in the order of tens or even hundreds of kHz . Most experimental investigations of surface heat transfer focus on the time variation of the wall temperature by using classical thermocouples or metal film gauges [4]. To-date, only a few investigators have been able to capture fluctuating heat transfer rates in SBLI flows through the use of dedicated sensor prototypes, namely Hayashi et al [5], and their results are quite different from recent numerical simulations, e.g Bernardini et al [6]. The present study aims to address this gap in the literature by presenting new measurements of fluctuating heat flux in two separated, turbulent SBLIs at a nominal Mach number of $Ma = 2$. The fluctuating heat flux at several positions on the SBLI streamwise axis is obtained using a fast-response ALTP (Atomic Layer Thermo Pile) sensor [7] that is based on the Transverse Seebeck Effect [8]. In this paper we compare these new results with unsteady wall pressure measurements and identify similarities but also several interesting differences that raise interesting questions for future investigations. The presented results may still be qualified as preliminary, inasmuch as the spatial resolution of the measurement is rather low. Nevertheless, interesting differences observed in the fluctuating pressure and heat-flux signatures already warrant their presentation at a dedicated conference.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1 Experimental Facility and Flow Test Case

The experimental campaign was carried out in the high-speed wind tunnel at the Chair of Aerodynamics of *Technische Universität Berlin*. The facility is an open loop, indraft wind tunnel capable of continuous operation

Figure 1: Schematic representation of the high-speed wind tunnel at *TU Berlin* with a focus on the turbulent SBLI test section. [9]

at Mach numbers of up to 2.3 with atmospheric stagnation conditions. An in-depth review of the facility can be found in Rohlfs et al. [9] and a schematic representation is shown in Fig. 1. The test section for the present study has a cross-section of $150 \text{ mm} \times 150 \text{ mm}$ and is equipped with a fixed Laval nozzle to create a nominal inflow Mach number of 2.0 with a typical unit Reynolds number of $Re \approx 12.5 \times 10^6 \text{ m}^{-1}$. The stagnation conditions are atmospheric and the recovery to total temperature ratio of the test section was measured at $T_R/T_o = 0.985$. This indicates that the flow is nearly adiabatic, with near-zero mean heat fluxes $\bar{q} \approx 0$.

Different wedges can be mounted inside the test section to introduce shockwaves of various strengths into the flow. When the shock impinges on the wind-tunnel floor, it interacts with the fully turbulent boundary layer with a thickness of $\delta_0 = 7 \text{ mm}$, thus creating an oblique shockwave/boundary-layer interaction. For the present study, deflection angles of 8° and 10° were chosen to create SBLIs that are considered medium- and high-strength interactions in the literature.

The resulting flow topology is shown in Fig. 2 and a Schlieren image for the 10° flow deflection can be seen in Fig. 3. The strong adverse pressure gradient generated by the impinging shock leads to a separation of the boundary layer which in turn creates a reversed flow region between the *separation point* S and the *reattachment point* R , with the characteristic length L_{sep} . The deflection caused by the bubble induces converging compression waves in the incoming flow that merge into a *separation shock*, thus forming the characteristic λ -foot of the separated SBLI. Another important parameter to consider for the following investigations is the interaction length L_{int} defined as the distance between the extrapolated impingement point x_{imp} (from inviscid shock theory) and the interaction on-

Figure 2: Schematic representation of an incident turbulent Shockwave Boundary-Layer Interaction. The white circles are representing the positions of the ALTP sensors.

set x_0 where the wall pressure starts to rise. To compare different configurations, the streamwise coordinate x is offset by the interaction onset and normalized with the interaction length to create the lengthscale X^* used in Fig. 3, see Rohlfs et al. for details[9].

2.2 Instrumentation

Measurements were performed with both fluctuating pressure transducers and heat-flux sensors. All instruments are mounted in the wind tunnel through an insert with six measurement positions for each sensor type. They are distributed evenly over the length of the interaction as shown in Fig. 2, with the first position under the upstream boundary layer and the last position around the reattachment point with $X^* \approx 1$ for the 10° case.

Figure 3: Schlieren image of a strong Interaction created by a 10° flow deflection.

2.2.1 Atomic Layer Thermopiles (ALTP)

Atomic Layer Thermopiles (ALTP) make use of the Transverse Seebeck Effect (TSE) and measure heat flux signals at the wall with a high frequency resolution of up to 1 – 2 MHz [10, 11]. The ALTP film consists of a approx. 500 nanometer thick, tilted layered structure which is made of Yttrium, Barium and Copperoxide (YBCO) and CuO_2 grown on a SrTiO_3 cylindrical substrate.

To achieve maximum measurement bandwidth, uncoated sensors with a small active layer size of 1×1 mm are used. Based on the TSE, an electrical field is created if a temperature difference ΔT across the tilted structure (active layer) is present [8]. The measured output voltage U_{ALTP} is generated by the active layer (see Fig. 4) and can be characterized by Eq. 1,

$$U_{\text{ALTP}} = \frac{l \sin 2\gamma \Delta S \Delta T}{2d} \quad (1)$$

where l is the length of the active film, d is the thickness of the active film, and γ is the tilt angle. ΔS is the difference of the Seebeck coefficients of YBCO and CuO_2 . The sensors output voltage can be proportionally related to the heat flux over 11 orders of magnitude by a radiation calibration process [12].

The ALTP sensors in this study are based on SrTiO_3 substrates mounted in a thermoplastic housing with 8 mm diameter. More details on the sensor module and its configuration and dimensions can be found in Figure 5. Custom-made low noise DC- to 1 MHz amplifiers with a fixed gain of ≈ 5000 are used in order to amplify the signal of each ALTP. The surface of the module is flat and could be perfectly flush mounted with the wind tunnel wall. The manufacturer of the substrate (Fortech HTS [14]) provides a static sensitivity in the range $30 - 80 \mu\text{V cm}^2 \text{W}^{-1}$ depending on the active area with an uncertainty of $\approx 20\%$ obtained from radiation-

Figure 4: Active ALTP layer grown on SrTiO_3 -substrates with tilt angle γ [13].

Figure 5: Schematic of the ALTP sensor module (based on [10], dimensions in millimeter).

based calibration.

For this study we have conducted a supporting and more precise convective calibration of the ALTP modules. This was done in a subsonic calibration facility based on a 750°C hot air jet impinging normally on a baffle plate. More details on this experiment can be found in [13]. The convective calibration can not be used for absolute calibration but offers the possibility to perform a substitutional calibration with a reference sensor that is precisely calibrated beforehand with a laser calibration method [13]. The results of the convective procedure are displayed in Table 1.

Table 1: Results of the ALTP sensors in the convective calibration in comparison to a reference sensor for 2 heat levels.

	Reference sensor	ALTP 1	ALTP 2	ALTP 3	ALTP 4	ALTP 5	ALTP 6
Sensitivity in $\mu\text{V cm}^2 \text{W}^{-1}$ for heat level 1	108	63.6	67.4	75.1	44.8	43.2	38.9
Sensitivity in $\mu\text{V cm}^2 \text{W}^{-1}$ for heat level 2	108	65.3	71.8	77.6	45.6	45.4	37.3
RMS Sensitivity in $\mu\text{V cm}^2 \text{W}^{-1}$	108	64.5	69.6	76.4	45.2	44.3	38.1
rel. σ	1 %	2.7 %	6.5 %	3.6 %	2.8 %	6.8 %	4.0 %

2.2.2 Unsteady Wall Pressure

Wall pressure fluctuations are acquired using fast response pressure transducers (Kulite XCQ-062). The transducers have a bandwidth of over 30kHz and are mounted flush into the tunnel floor. The signals for both sensor types are fed through an analog 50 kHz low-pass filter, amplified, and then acquired with a National Instrument NI-USB 6353 data acquisition card at a sample-rate of 500kHz. The spectral analysis was conducted using the Welch method by splitting the data into 133 window segments with 33% overlap .

3. RESULTS

In this section the results of the measurement campaign are presented. First we will analyze the data in the temporal domain to highlight basic properties of the unsteadiness before switching to the frequency domain and analyzing the spectral content.

3.1 Fluctuations of Heat-Flux and Pressure

As a first point of comparison, Fig. 6 shows the RMS-values of the pressure and heat flux signals at different positions over the interaction for the two shock strengths. While the spatial resolution is quite low, we can still observe a clear variation of the unsteadiness along the SBLI and derive some interesting trends. For the pressure, the expected distribution features a strong peak around the interaction onset ($X^* = 0$) due to the oscillating shock foot [15, 16]. In the present dataset the peak is not resolved for any deflection angles, but the strong gradient between the first points indicates the presence of the oscillations. Inside the interaction zone the pressure fluctuations are smaller, but the rms is still significantly larger than in the upstream boundary layer. Towards the back of the interaction the unsteadiness increases again for the 10° case due to the developing shear layer behind the separation bubble while remaining almost constant for the 8° case. This is in good agreement with the results of Threadgill et al. [16] who also compared a range of incident reflections.

Figure 6: Distribution of the rms-values of pressure (black) and heat flux (red). The values are normalized by the fluctuation level of the upstream boundary layer

The heat flux signals q_{rms} are also higher than in the upstream boundary layer, however there are some key differences compared to the pressure signals. First, the gradient at the interaction onset appears to be much lower than for the pressure fluctuations, which indicates a shallower or no peak at all in the region of the separation shock foot. Without a higher spatial resolution this cannot be concluded definitively, but the results from the next section in the frequency domain support this argument. Second, underneath the separation bubble the values the heat flux RMS q_{rms} drop considerably and, especially for the 10° case, are only marginally larger than the upstream fluctuations. This is most likely due to the relatively low velocity fluctuations that lead to lower local heat flux fluctuations close the wall. Finally, there is an increase of the fluctuating heat flux towards the back of the interaction that is much stronger than the pressure fluctuations at this position. Around $X^* = 1$ the value for q_{rms} is almost four times larger than the upstream fluctuation level for the 10° case while p_{rms} only reaches around $2.7p_{rms}^{up}$. The 8° case exhibits a similar behavior with a clear increase in heat flux unsteadiness in contrast to the almost constant p_{rms} distribution.

Figure 7: Streamwise distribution of wall pressure fluctuation premultiplied PSDs under an incident SBLI generated by a 10° shock generator.

3.2 Spectral Analysis

To further analyze the unsteadiness development over the SBLI and evaluate the impact of the reflected shock motion on the wall heat-flux fluctuations, we present pre-multiplied spectra of the wall pressure and the instantaneous heat flux. These spectra are related to an SBLI obtained with the 10° SG, a flow case with extended separation, which is expected to demonstrate the low-frequency shock motion more obviously.

The waterfall plot (Fig. 7) of the streamwise distribution of the wall pressure fluctuations shows the typical patterns seen in the literature [17, 18, 9], with the frequency ranges divided into separate zones, each with distinct temporal scales:

- A high frequency zone (HFZ) ahead of the interaction, at $X^* \approx -0.2$, where the spectra have a bump-like shape, similar to what is observed in canonical wall-bounded flows. The peak frequency is of the order of $St_L > O(1)$, which is related to the energetic turbulent structures in the undisturbed boundary layer. It is important to note that the maximum frequency is underestimated here due to the transducers cutoff frequency and the low-pass filter used.
- A low frequency zone (LFZ) at the beginning of the interaction region near the foot of the reflected

Figure 8: Streamwise distribution of wall heat flux fluctuation premultiplied PSDs under an incident SBLI generated by a 10° shock generator.

shock, at around $X^* \approx 0$, characterized by very low frequency fluctuations with a broad peak centered at $St_L \approx 0.04 - 0.05$. This secondary peak is a distinct sign of the large-scale, low-frequency motion of the reflected shock.

- An intermediate frequency zone (IFZ), corresponding to the interaction zone $-0.2 \leq X^* \leq 1$, with spectra of shape similar to the incoming boundary layer. Here the frequency range has broadened and the peak has shifted to slightly lower frequencies due to the thickening of the boundary layer [6]. The value of the Strouhal number ($St_L \approx 1$) falls between the low frequencies of the reflected shock motion and the high frequencies of the fine-grained turbulence.

The analysis of the power spectral density of the heat transfer coefficient in Fig. 8 reveals a contrasting view. As it is evident from the big peak in the waterfall plot, there is a significant increase in the intensity of the heat flux fluctuations near the reattachment point close to the end of the interaction zone at $X^* \approx 1$. The peak is shifted towards intermediate frequencies of approximately $St_L \approx 1$, which is typically linked to the shedding of vortical structures in the shear layer that develops over the shock-induced separation bubble[19]. As more clearly evident in Fig. 9, showing a comparison between the pre-mul-

Figure 9: Premultiplied PSDs distribution of wall pressure fluctuations (black) and heat flux fluctuations (red) under an incident SBLI generated by a 10° shock generator.

tiplied PSDs of the pressure and the heat flux fluctuations, there is no indication of any strong low-frequency activity in the proximity of the reflected shock foot (LFZ- $X^* \approx 0$), except maybe a small hump at $St_L \approx 0.1$. Indeed the majority of the energy is concentrated at intermediate to high frequencies around $St_L \approx 1$ throughout the interaction. This suggests that in the flow cases being studied, the primary factor contributing to the peak heating in the interaction zone is the turbulence amplification resulting from the SBLI. This findings appear to be in agreement with what was already discovered in the DNS simulation performed by Bernardini et. al[6].

The 8° shock generator test case present the same exact behaviour as the 10° case as can be readily observed in Fig. 9 and Fig. 10. Indeed, the streamwise variation of both pressure and heat flux spectra are similar for both SG angles.

Although the present results find positive feedback

Figure 10: Premultiplied PSDs distribution of wall pressure fluctuations (black) and heat flux fluctuations (red) under an incident SBLI generated by a 8° shock generator.

with the cited numerical simulation, further investigations are needed. Specifically, by improving the spatial resolution of the measuring setup, it will be possible to capture more accurately the full extent of the reflected shock foot motion and gain a better understanding of the differences noted between pressure and heat-flux fluctuations.

4. CONCLUSION

The fluctuating heat flux in a family of turbulent, incident shock/boundary layer interactions has been investigated. Fast-response ALTP sensors were integrated into the wind-tunnel floor and measurements at different positions in the interaction were performed. Strong unsteadiness over a broad range of frequencies was captured with good temporal resolution highlighting the feasibility of the measurement method. The maximum amplitude of

the fluctuating heat-flux was found towards the back of the interaction at frequencies around $St_{L_{int}} \approx 1$. When comparing the results with fluctuating pressure measurements, the signals show a similar trend, but a clear difference is the absence of low-frequency unsteadiness around the separation shock foot in the heat-flux data. While this finding agrees with numerical results, it clearly raises new questions about the reason for this difference and shows a need for future investigations with increased spatial resolution.

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